

EOSC-Pillar

Exploring reference data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics community

Use Case 6 final report

Yosra Sanaa¹, Marwa Belhaj-Salem¹, Gilles Mathieu¹, Pietro Mandreoli^{3,6}, Marco Antonio Tangaro^{3,4}, Giacinto Donvito⁴, Nadina Foggetti⁴, Marica Antonacci⁴, Christophe Blanchet^{2,5}, Laura Burlot^{2,5}, Jonathan Lorenzo^{2,5}, Daniele Colombo⁶, Federico Zambelli^{3,6}, David Salgado^{1,7}, and Christophe Béroud^{1,7}

¹National Institute of Health and Medical Research “Inserm”

²French Institute of Bioinformatics “IFB”

³Institute of Biomembranes Bioenergetics and Molecular Biotechnology
“CNR-IBIOM”

⁴National Institute for Nuclear Physics “INFN”

⁵French National Centre for Scientific Research “CNRS”

⁶University of Milan

⁷Aix-Marseille University

December 2022

Lead Partner	INSERM/DSI
Contributing Partners	INFN, CNR/IBIOM, CNRS/IFB
Version	1
Status	Final
Dissemination Level	Public
Document Link	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7543550

Abstract

EOSC-Pillar was a project funded by the European Union’s H2020 research and innovation program, running from July 2019 to December 2022. It aimed to coordinate national Open Science efforts across Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy, and ensure their contribution and readiness for the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The project included a work package dedicated to use cases, whose aim was to demonstrate the added value of EOSC level services and coordination for specific communities.

This document is a complete report of the work achieved during the project on Use case 6: Exploring reference data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics community. It presents identified scientific and technical challenges, use case objectives, solutions put in place, exploitable results and perspectives for future work.

Contents

1	Introduction	4
1.1	The EOSC-Pillar project	4
1.2	EOSC-Pillar WP6: scientific usecases	5
2	UC 6.6 presentation	6
2.1	Global objectives	6
2.2	Targeted community	6
2.3	Challenges addressed	6
2.4	Team and partners	7
3	Scientific description	8
3.1	Theoretical scenarios	8
3.1.1	Building up on user stories	8
3.1.2	Scenario 1: Public Galaxy instance(s)	8
3.1.3	Scenario 2: Close-to-the-data deployment	8
3.1.4	Scenario 3: Health data with restricted access	9
3.1.5	Scenario 4: Reproducibility and verification	9
3.1.6	global view and architecture of all scenarios	9
3.2	Concrete application to hCNV detection	11
3.2.1	Human Copy Number Variation (hCNV): Scientific Context	11
3.2.2	Challenge to address	11
3.2.3	How EOSC-Pillar Usecase 6 can help	11
4	Implementation and technical description	12
4.1	Underlying services	12
4.1.1	Galaxy - Laniakea	12
4.1.2	Inserm repository	12
4.1.3	Federated FAIR Dataspace (F2DS)	13
4.2	Preparatory work	13
4.2.1	"Deploying Galaxy" state of the art as of 2020	13
4.2.2	Data formats and data sources	16
4.2.3	Choosing the dataset for the demonstrator	16

4.3	Implementation of the 4 theoretical scenarios	16
4.3.1	Global organisation: how each scenario fits in the landscape	16
4.3.2	Galaxy workflow common to all 4 scenarios	17
4.3.3	Populating data sources in the F2DS	18
4.3.4	Scenario 1: Public Galaxy instance(s)	19
4.3.5	Scenario 2: Close-to-the-data deployment	19
4.3.6	Scenario 3: Health data with restricted access	20
4.3.7	Scenario 4: Reproducibility and verification	21
4.4	Building a demonstrator on the hCNV application	21
4.4.1	Proposed environment/architecture	21
4.4.2	Proposed scenario	22
4.4.3	Used data	23
4.4.4	Used Tools	23
4.4.5	Feedback and perspectives	23
5	Conclusion	24
5.1	Usecase outputs	24
5.1.1	Key exploitable results	24
5.1.2	Services and tools	24
5.1.3	Guidelines and best practices	24
5.1.4	Outreach and community involvement	25
5.1.5	Remaining blocking points	25
5.2	Possible future work	25
5.2.1	Follow up on project actions	25
5.2.2	Exploitation of key results	26
5.2.3	potential use by other communities	26
A	Deliverables, online resources and documentation	27
A.1	Online ressources and project deliverables	27
A.2	Presentations, talks and posters during events	28
B	Annexes	29
B.1	Data formats	29
B.1.1	Sequence data	29
B.1.2	Genome Annotations	29
B.1.3	Data for mapping	30
B.1.4	General Formats	30
B.2	Existing data sources in bioinformatics	31

1 Introduction

1.1 The EOSC-Pillar project

The EOSC-Pillar project was funded by the European Union's H2020 research and innovation program, and ran from July 1st, 2019 to December 31st, 2022. The following is an excerpt from the project website¹:

"EOSC-Pillar aims to coordinate national Open Science efforts across Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy, and ensure their contribution and readiness for the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

The project aims to assist in the coordination and harmonization of national initiatives pertinent to EOSC in Europe, investigate the possibility of them federating in the future, aid in the integration of initiatives and data/cloud providers through the development of common policies and tools, and assist user communities in adopting and using these services as well as suggest brand-new ones born from their scientific domain. In order to do this, the project will combine a top-down and a bottom-up strategy (by voicing the needs and requirements indicated by the many scientific communities working at the national level) (by harmonising the national strategies and translating them in a viable work plan). Longer term, it is anticipated that this will make it easier to create and adopt common policies, simplify the EOSC membership process for service providers and user communities, and help fill the EOSC with useful services of greater European interest based on the actual needs and interests of the European scientific communities. The project will work with associated regional and theme efforts to maximize this simplification approach.

The EOSC is envisioned to offer 1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science, technology, the humanities and social sciences a virtual environment with open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines by federating existing scientific data infrastructures, currently dispersed across disciplines and the EU Member States.

The project has the ambition to propose the initiatives for the national coordination of data infrastructures and service recently started in many Member States as one of the founding pillars for the construction, development and long-term sustainability of the EOSC. Coherently with this vision, it starts with an initial group of neighbouring countries who are active in the field of open science, to define and set a model to harmonise and interfederate the initiatives. The real challenge here is that, despite having very similar objectives and visions, and similar compositions, the initiatives adopt different approaches, need to abide by different national laws and regulations and have very different funding models and relations with the decision makers: for this reason, the task of harmonise the different national experiences is not a trivial one, but succeeding in it means to bring in the picture all the advantages that the adaptation to national peculiarities brings. EOSC-Pillar takes the challenge to build on such specificities and heterogeneity to enhance the level of collaboration among all the countries bringing a rich and well organised contribution to EOSC. In a motto, pursuing unity in diversity."

¹<https://eosc-pillar.eu/project>

1.2 EOSC-Pillar WP6: scientific usecases

EOSC-Pillar's Work Package 6² provides use cases for analyzing various tools and services for the "FAIRization" of data and services as well as the type of governance to meet community demands.

Utilization instances are gathered in this work package in accordance with the needs of the scientific communities. Pilots are conducted to test the proposed solutions, which are intended to be global and general enough to be applied to other communities with little modification.

The main objectives of this work package are to:

- Analyse specificities of the scientific communities but also cross-cutting needs
- Integrate different data from all components and domains and facilitate access, integrated and intelligent treatments and diffusion
- Identify important tools and services from the use cases
- Identify gaps and needs that can be fulfilled by the future EOSC
- Expand the set of use cases through the launch of an open call for communities

The initial set of scientific use cases was expanded through an open call for participation, inviting communities and their developers to bring forward thematic services to enhance the portfolio of the project and the EOSC Portal.

²<https://eosc-pillar.eu/use-cases>

2 UC 6.6 presentation

2.1 Global objectives

Galaxy³ is one of the best-known workflow management systems for bioinformatics, aiming to make computational biology accessible to research scientists that do not have computer programming or systems administration experience.

How can researchers smoothly integrate this potent tool with a variety of data sources? How may they use various instances of Galaxy to accomplish this in a logical manner? Can it be used locally or on a protected network that manages patient data? Can they compare the outcomes of those several possibilities? These are the primary issues this use-case seeks to resolve.

The use-case aims at creating standards and best practices, establish a service prototype based on several scientific scenarios, and build upon current French and Italian national services, to:

1. Enable EOSC access to reference data from several Galaxy deployments
2. Make it easier to deploy Galaxy instances close to the data
3. Ensure consistency among existing Galaxy deployments
4. Ensure that all health data security requirements are met throughout the process

2.2 Targeted community

Usecase 6 has its roots within the bioinformatics community, which has the main following specificities:

- A huge need in computing power and storage resources
- A very varied and heterogeneous landscape in terms of tools, services, applications and platforms used for research
- Strong legal requirements linked to the use of health data

The community is structured around ELIXIR⁴, an intergovernmental organisation that brings together life science resources from across Europe. Both the French and Italian nodes of Elixir were partners of the T6.6 task. Although many progress have been made in the last decade, it is to be noted that many services and tools used within the community are not FAIR by design. FAIRisation of tools and data are therefore a major objective on which EOSC related projects can help.

2.3 Challenges addressed

Galaxy is a widely used tool and comes in many flavours. One of the first challenges to address is the reproducibility and coherency of the different deployments to ensure that data analysis workflows produce the same results whatever the instance used. This means

³<https://usegalaxy.org/>

⁴<https://elixir-europe.org/>

technical work within Galaxy itself, but also a global reflection on how to connect different data sources to Galaxy in a simple and coherent way.

Another challenge is the need to conform to data protection regulations concerning health personal data, by deploying Galaxy in a private, secured environment while still ensuring the data analysis workflow remains similar to its public counterpart.

Finally, we must find a way of providing access to the service to all users within the EOSC community through roles management and by integrating it into a global authentication framework.

2.4 Team and partners

The T6.6 project brought together the following partners and individuals:

- National Institute of Health and Medical Research “Inserm”;
 - Yosra Sanaa
 - Marwa Belhaj-Salem
 - Gilles Mathieu
- French Institute of Bioinformatics “IFB”;
 - Christophe Blanchet
 - Jonathan Lorenzo
 - Laura Burlot
- Institute of Biomembranes Bioenergetics and Molecular Biotechnology “CNR-IBIOM”;
 - Marco Antonio Tangaro
 - Pietro Mandreoli
 - Federico Zambelli
 - Graziano Pesole
- National Institute for Nuclear Physics “INFN”
 - Giacinto Donvito
 - Marica Antonacci
 - Nadina Foggetti

Beyond the initial T6.6 team, the task got support and effort from David Salgado and Christophe Bérout (Inserm U911) for the work on hCNV application.

3 Scientific description

3.1 Theoretical scenarios

3.1.1 Building up on user stories

The needs and challenges expressed when designing this use case can be explicitated through different user stories. Some of them follow:

- As a researcher, I would like to access a subset of genomics data from a given cohort in order to perform analysis/computation on these data without having to transfer them.
- As a bioinformatician (Galaxy user) I would like to know how to format my data in order to ensure it can be used properly throughout my workflows
- As a data provider (health data) I would like to be sure the data I'm taking care of are both properly secured and yet accessible to various computational tools so that they can be useful to researchers
- As a developer, I would like to be able to deploy Galaxy on different Cloud infrastructures across Europe transparently in order to implement and make available new tools and workflows very quickly on the different data spaces available to me.
- As a healthcare provider interested in personalized medicine, I would like to be able to use GDPR compliant Galaxy instances deployed over Cloud infrastructures across Europe so I could safely process patients data.

These user stories represent examples of real life situation, and are impersonating the needs this use case wants to address. Their analysis led to define different scenarios, that are presented in the next sections.

3.1.2 Scenario 1: Public Galaxy instance(s)

A user must implement a Galaxy workflow that requires input data from institutional repositories (such as the Inserm repository) or data from a public database. This can be accomplished using a Galaxy public server, in our prototype hosted on an EOSC-Pillar partner infrastructure (INFN), and by searching and accessing required input data in the EOSC Pillar Federated dataspace. Finally, output data are transferred to an institutional repository/storage.

3.1.3 Scenario 2: Close-to-the-data deployment

A user needs to perform analysis on big files (and/or many files) through an I/O intensive workflow, but he doesn't want to or it is not possible to upload data on a public Galaxy instance. He obtains the necessary information about data location and nearby infrastructures from the federated dataspace. He can easily deploy a private Galaxy instance on a nearby infrastructure. The same approach can be used because this Galaxy instance has the same characteristics as the main one. Output data can be stored locally, and referenced in a institutional repository.

3.1.4 Scenario 3: Health data with restricted access

Users must do analysis on a dataset (personal/health data) that is subject to strict legal regulations. This dataset can only be accessed from a protected environment as a result, and using Galaxy in such a setting is subject to tight guidelines and regulations. They gather information about the dataset from the federated dataspace, along with information on how access requests are processed. Once they have access to the data, they can use a private Galaxy instance in a secure environment to do the study. When possible, output data is populated elsewhere and referenced in an institutional repository in addition to being stored inside the perimeter of these protected environments.

3.1.5 Scenario 4: Reproducibility and verification

The user must compare the workflows and/or outcomes from scenarios 1, 2, and 3. He must make sure that analyses were created using the same methodology for that, and if there are any differences, he must be able to spot them. He should also be able to duplicate the outcomes of such events.

3.1.6 global view and architecture of all scenarios

The main idea is to use datasets published in different repositories, and reference them in a Federated Data Space environment. The next schema shows how the different scenarios complement each other, depending on where the analysis (through Galaxy) will run. The harmonisation of Galaxy deployments should ensure similar results on the 3 first scenarios, an hypothesis that will be tested in the 4th scenario.

3.2 Concrete application to hCNV detection

3.2.1 Human Copy Number Variation (hCNV): Scientific Context

Most human cells divide through a process called mitosis, in which one parent cell splits into two daughter cells. A cell makes a copy of its own DNA just before dividing, but this copy might not have the same gene sequence as the parent DNA. One gene, for instance, might be duplicated twice in the new DNA or not at all. The term for this occurrence is Copy Number Variation (CNV).

These copy number variations are believed to be crucial for evolution, but they also have a significant impact on some diseases. Despite Copy Number Variations being the most common genetic mutation type, it is still very difficult to recognize and interpret them..

For more information, see the Elixir hCNV community web page⁵, from which the text above is extracted.

3.2.2 Challenge to address

The ELIXIR hCNV Community aims to implement processes to make the detection, annotation and interpretation of these variations easier. One of the task that the community is working on is the benchmarking of different CNV callers, which are the tools used to detect CNV.

Through its *Genome in a Bottle* programme⁶, The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) publishes reference hCNV data. To benchmark different tools, the idea is to launch a CNV detection workflow using a given caller on a reference sample provided by the NIST, and then compare obtained result to the gold standard corresponding to that sample to evaluate the efficiency/quality of used caller.

To avoid biases and optimise the benchmarking, we need to ensure that all benchmarks run in a similar environment, and that used workflows are as independent from the underlying infrastructure as possible. We also want to ensure that obtained results are still relevant if we launch real studies, using other data sources than reference data.

3.2.3 How EOSC-Pillar Usecase 6 can help

The environment set up in the context of EOSC-Pillar Usecase 6 presents many advantages for addressing presented challenges.

Running CNV Callers on Galaxy is a way to ensure neutrality with regards to the platform on which the tools are tested. By testing them on the Laniakea@ReCAS service (see section 4.1.1), we can guarantee similar execution conditions throughout the tests and validate further comparisons.

Getting data through an standard way using EOSC-Pillar F2DS (see section 4.1.3) is a second advantage, as it ensures both test data and gold standard data are gathered in a similar way, facilitating the whole process.

Finally, this environment allows for reuse of a single workflow, changing only the application that is used as CNV caller.

⁵<https://elixir-europe.org/communities/hcnv>

⁶<https://www.nist.gov/programs-projects/genome-bottle>

4 Implementation and technical description

4.1 Underlying services

4.1.1 Galaxy - Laniakea

Used Galaxy service is provided by EOSC-Pillar T7.4 “Ready-to-use” Laniakea@ReCAS service⁷. It is already available and provides bioinformatics analysis tools to the Elixir Italian and European community. The Laniakea@ReCaS service allows end users to easily deploy Galaxy private instances.

Galaxy is a simple yet powerful web-based workflow manager, where it is easy to import, manage, perform analysis on users’ datasets and then share results and workflows. This improves reproducibility and contributes in offloading researchers of many menial tasks, allowing them to better focus on interpreting any evidence harnessed from data. Furthermore, of particular importance is the possibility to quite easily import into the workflow manager a wealth of external data that are already available on public repositories. Laniakea provides the possibility to deploy different instance configurations, in terms of CPUs, RAM and storage.

Finally, it provides easy access and management of reference data is available with systems in place to avoid any unnecessary redundancy. In fact, a CVMFS⁸ based storage ensures that all the Galaxy instances supported by the Laniakea service share access to a rich common set of reference data that can however be expanded by users of single instances if needed.

The INDIGO PaaS layer⁹, which is the core middleware of Laniakea, recently made available the possibility to deploy and configure Virtual Machines (VM) on private networks. This means that the VMs are completely isolated from the external world and can be reached only through a properly configured VPN/bastion. The reference setup for the VPN server is based on OpenVPN and a PAM (Pluggable Authentication Modules) module has been developed in order to extend the authentication and authorization mechanism using the INDIGO IAM¹⁰ service. Finally, Laniakea allows the creation and the management of encrypted storage associated with these instances, thus improving the isolation and safety of these virtual environments. An overview of how the service can be used, as well as how the interface looks like, is presented in a video demo available online¹¹.

4.1.2 Inserm repository

One of the key aspects of Open Science is the publication and referencing of research datasets in appropriate repositories. As part of this project, datasets were published on a variety of platforms provided by our partner INRAe¹². We began by utilizing a test Dataverse¹³ instance provided on the *Ouvrir la science*¹⁴ platform.

⁷https://laniakea-elixir-it.github.io/laniakea_at_recas

⁸<https://cernvm.cern.ch/fs/>

⁹<https://www.indigo-datacloud.eu/paas-orchestrator>

¹⁰<https://www.indigo-datacloud.eu/identity-and-access-management>

¹¹<https://youtu.be/WZey8XrCp1I>

¹²<https://www.inrae.fr/>

¹³<https://dataverse.org/>

¹⁴<https://www.ouvrirelascience.fr>

As the project matured, we were able to start using newly built Inserm's institutional repository, hosted on the French National platform *Recherche Data Gov*¹⁵. This institutional repository, called EDI (standing for "*Entrepôt de Données Inserm*", Inserm Data Repository)¹⁶, provides data generated as part of research projects funded or promoted by Inserm (in the case of research involving humans). All scientific staff from Inserm structures (researcher, engineer, technician) can make a deposit in EDI, regardless of the organization that pays them. The most sensitive data (identification risk, economic risk, and so on) are kept in other warehouses for ad hoc protection, and can be referenced in EDI.

4.1.3 Federated FAIR Dataspace (F2DS)

The Federated FAIR Data Space (F2DS) provides tools for both data producers and data consumers to improve the overall FAIRness of datasets that are natively dispersed across heterogeneous repositories by implementing services for dataset homogenisation, enrichment, and onboarding, as well as services for seamless discovery and access.

Researchers will be able to search for, locate, and retrieve data using the F2DS, which has a single access point and a set of tools. Because it hides the various access points from various sources and provides a single access point via user and programming interfaces (UI and API), it not only saves time on the job but can also produce new insights, provided the right combination of selected search criteria and content from one or more data sets is examined concurrently.

A detailed description of the F2DS toolset is presented on EOSC-Pillar website¹⁷, and in project deliverables D5.3¹⁸ and D5.6¹⁹

4.2 Preparatory work

4.2.1 "Deploying Galaxy" state of the art as of 2020

This sections shows part of the assessment work done at the beginning of the project.

Official Galaxy portal deployment modes

The Galaxy portal can be set up for a variety of uses, from a single user perspective to a production portal (official deployment modes are available online from the Galaxy Project website²⁰).

Simple deployment for a single user is as follows:

- Duplicate the repository
- Run the installation script

More advanced modes include the use of several dedicated software components and/or manual/automatic configurations:

¹⁵<https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/>

¹⁶<https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataverse/inserm>

¹⁷<https://eosc-pillar.eu/federated-fair-data-space-f2ds>

¹⁸<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5513795>

¹⁹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5720411>

²⁰<https://galaxyproject.org/admin/get-galaxy>

- Manual configuration of advanced components:
 - DBMS as PostgreSQL instead of SQLite
 - Dedicated HTTP server like Apache or Nginx, instead of the built-in one
 - External authentication and authorization systems like SAML or OIDC
- Automatic installation can be done through
 - Configuration management system like Ansible with the GalaxyKickStart play-book
 - All-in-one with a built Docker image

Recently the Galaxy community has released the official Ansible roles for Galaxy deployment²¹

Deployment in IFB clouds federation

Users of the French IFB²² cloud federation can deploy several flavors of Galaxy portals in their own virtual machines (See RAINBio apps catalogue for details about the available apps²³).

A basic Galaxy installation is based on a Docker image of the Galaxy portal and a git-based repository to deploy the virtual machine. Users can also choose pre-defined environments through a specific deployment parameter (`galaxy_stack`) corresponding to the Docker image to use in the virtual machine deployment.

No supplementary tools are added to the used Docker images but each deployed Galaxy portal can be customized by the users in a usual way with the admin mode. Indeed, each deployment set its own admin password, displayed to the user/owner in the Biosphere portal once the cloud deployment is running.

Deployment in Laniakea

The user interacts with a Laniakea-based service through a simple front-end that allows a general setup of a Galaxy instance, and then Laniakea takes care of the automatic deployment of the virtual hardware and the software components. At the end of the process, the user gains access with full administrative privileges to a private, production-grade, fully customisable, Galaxy virtual instance and to the underlying virtual machine (VM). Laniakea features deployment of single-server or cluster-backed Galaxy instances, sharing of reference data across multiple instances, data volume encryption, and support for VM image-based, Docker-based, and Ansible roles-based Galaxy deployments. The Galaxy environment is installed using custom Ansible roles.

Laniakea has three different deployment strategies:

- **Galaxy live build:** This version is recommended for those users which want to be sure to have the latest available version of each tool. The Galaxy production environment²⁴ is installed on the VM from scratch using Ansible roles ; the tools and workflows are installed through Ansible role in the latest available version

²¹<https://galaxyproject.github.io/training-material/topics/admin/tutorials/ansible-galaxy/tutorial.html>

²²<https://www.france-bioinformatique.fr/>

²³<https://biosphere.france-bioinformatique.fr/catalogue>

²⁴<https://docs.galaxyproject.org/en/latest/admin/production.html>

- **Galaxy express:** This version is usually quite reliable and work well for most users. The Galaxy express instantiates a CentOS 7 Virtual Machine with Galaxy production environment already installed and configured with all its companion software and the set of tools.
- **Galaxy Docker:** the Laniakea Galaxy Docker application run a Galaxy Docker container inside a Centos 7 virtual machine. The Official Galaxy Docker image is used²⁵.

All these deployment strategies use Laniakea specific Ansible roles. More information can be found in Laniakea online documentation²⁶. A video that explain the deployment process from the user point of view is also available online²⁷.

The Laniakea team is working to use the official Galaxy project Ansible role instead of Laniakea custom roles to deploy Galaxy instances. The use of the official roles of the Galaxy project will allow rapid updates (the Galaxy Project roles are updated immediately after the release of a version of Galaxy), making it easier to maintain the Laniakea framework.

Tools integration and dataset import

There are several ways of integrating tools²⁸:

- Manually from the portal and a toolshed
- Automatically with the install-tools command and a tools list in YAML format
- from command line using shed-tools install -a <API_KEY> -t <tool_list.yml>
- By running tools with external Docker containers
- With the API

There are several ways of importing datasets²⁹:

- Manually from the portal user's history
- Manually from the user folder
- With a script writing a '.loc' file
- With the API

Reference Data can be added to the VM attaching the official Galaxy CVMFS³⁰

²⁵<https://github.com/bgruening/docker-galaxy-stable>

²⁶<https://laniakea.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

²⁷<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cq-68-20n3Y>

²⁸<https://galaxyproject.org/admin/tools/add-tool-from-toolshed-tutorial/>

²⁹<https://galaxyproject.org/data-libraries/>

³⁰<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/admin/tutorials/cvmfs/tutorial.html>

4.2.2 Data formats and data sources

At the beginning of the project, the T6.6 team conducted a study on existing data sources in Bioinformatics and on main data formats used in this field. The result of this study is presented in Annexes.

4.2.3 Choosing the dataset for the demonstrator

As reference dataset, we used training data for somatic variant calling, which are completely open and are available online³¹.

The primary function of UC 6.6 is to illustrate the entire workflow. One of the most important services to test is the Laniakea service, provided by INFN and CNR/IBIOM, which is a specific implementation of Galaxy. It was decided to use a practice dataset for teaching biologists how to use Galaxy for that purpose.

Selecting the dataset is one of the most crucial steps. The initial thought was to select a straightforward and light dataset. The somatic variant calling was deemed a good candidate since it serves as a training dataset for biologists learning how to use Galaxy's workflows for variant calling. Somatic variant calling, the chosen dataset, is a very effective new tool used for the analysis of cancer sample. The dataset is made up of four files: the first two contain the forward and reverse reads sequence data from a patient's normal tissue, while the final two contain the data from that patient's tumor tissue.

4.3 Implementation of the 4 theoretical scenarios

4.3.1 Global organisation: how each scenario fits in the landscape

The initial design of the task in EOSC-Pillar Description of Work included 4 thematic subtasks, namely:

- **T6.6.1 - Share and harmonize Galaxy deployment practices.** The aim of this task is to develop and share experience on ongoing deployment solutions. Foreseen aspects include Ansible roles, Git repositories and Continuous Integration principles. The task will identify and develop best practices and improve them to cover the needs and the specificity of the different underlying infrastructures.
- **T6.6.2 - Facilitation of “Close to the data” computing.** Connecting computing services to large datasets highlights the need to have strong connections between computing facilities and data repositories. This task will look at limitations of currently available services, and identify missing services for making “computing close to the data” possible.
- **T6.6.3 - Data structure and formats.** This task will look at existing data, their current formats and structures. It will aim at identifying, and possibly putting into practice, solutions allowing for a facilitated integration with computing services, especially with regards to storage strategies, exchange formats, and the use of metadata.

³¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2582555>

- **T6.6.4 - Health data security aspects.** Legal and ethics requirements on the storage and handling of health data are very strong. In most cases, they can be obstacles to data sharing and interoperability. This subtask will look at how proposed solutions can be put in place while meeting those strong security requirements.

The table below shows how proposed scenarios fit with regards to these subtasks.

Scenario	1	2	3	4
	Public/ Open data	Big files, possibly open	Sensitive data / restricted access	Reproducibility
Reference repository(ies)	Inserm, IN-RAE, Public DB	Inserm	Inserm	All
Prerequisites	Source repositories connected to the FAIR Federated Data Space (WP5) Shared dictionaries/thesauri (WP5/6.6.3) Metadata format specification (WP5/6.6.3)			
Technical needs	API to search metadata (WP5/6.6.3) API to get datasets (WP5) Central service to run the analysis (WP7)	Interface to search metadata (WP5) Service ready-to-use to deploy locally (6.6.1/6.6.4)	Interface to search metadata (WP5) Service ready-to-use to deploy locally (6.6.1/6.6.4)	API to search metadata (WP5/6.6.3) API to get datasets (WP5) Central service to run the analysis (WP7)
Difficulties and obstacles to overcome	Search metadata globally (WP5/6.6.3) Coherent access to different sources (WP5/6.6.3)	Search metadata globally (WP5/6.6.3) Deploy Galaxy close to the data (6.6.2)	Search metadata globally (WP5/6.6.3) Deploy Galaxy in secure environment (6.6.4)	Search metadata globally (WP5/6.6.3) Ensure results are comparable (6.6.1)

4.3.2 Galaxy workflow common to all 4 scenarios

For demonstration purpose, and simple and light Galaxy workflow has been chosen to facilitate implementation of the four scenarios (small datasets, few technical requirements). We have used a training workflow available from the training galaxy project³².

The aims of this workflow is to identify somatic and germline variants, as well as variants affected by LOH, from a tumor and a normal sample of the same patient.

It allows to report the variant sites, and the genes affected by them, annotated with the content of general human genetic and cancer-specific databases.

³²<https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/variant-analysis/tutorials/somatic-variants/tutorial.html>

The workflow can be decomposed into the following steps:

1- At first, user need to upload and prepare input data to analyze. For this he creates a new history on Galaxy and give it a meaningful name. Then he imports the four files of the chosen dataset (see section 4.2.3) from Zenodo. In addition to the data, the user needs to import the genome (hg19 version of the sequences of human chromosomes 5,12 and 17).

Before starting, it is essential to check the quality of data, that there haven't been any major issues during DNA preparation, exon capture or during sequencing. For this, user run the tool FastQC on all fastq datasets.

The second tool MultiQC is used to aggregate the raw FastQC data of all input datasets into one report.

2- After checking the quality of data, user apply read trimming and filtering to see if all is well and to demonstrate the general concept. Running this tool generate 4 outputs datasets.

3- The next step is the read mapping by using BWA-MEM. It allows to map the reads from the normal tissue sample and others from the tumor tissue sample to the reference genome.

After mapping read, it is important to filter on mapped reads properties and removing duplicate reads. The last step before variant calling is to left-align reads around indels and recalibrate read mapping qualities.

4- After generated a high-quality set of mapped pairs it possible to move to variant calling and classification. The tool VarScan somatic is dedicated for somatic variant calling. It allows to detect variant alleles in tumor/normal sample pairs and call sample genotypes at variant sites. Also it classifies variants into germline, somatic and LOH event variants using solid classical statistics.

5- The last step of this workflow is "Variant annotation and reporting". There is five substeps start with getting data until adding additional annotation to the gene-centered report.

This workflow is available online from Laniakea Github repository³³

4.3.3 Populating data sources in the F2DS

The F2ds toolset is made up of two complementary services, the data catalogue service and the metadata repository service. The metadata repository is used to collect and to enhance datasets, the semantic enrichment service is also linked to the metadata repository.

After publishing the dataset in the original repository, the researcher must connect to the F2DS toolset to begin the metadata enrichment process. The idea is to build a data repository layer that is linked together by a federation of APIs. The principle is to build connectors that are described using the openApi standard. As a result, the data repository layer is linked to the smart harvester.

The first step is to establish a metadata repository and update the API description so that the metadata harvester harvests metadata from a repository using those APIs.

³³<https://github.com/Laniakea-elixir-it/Galaxy-flavours/tree/master/galaxy-pillar>

The second step is to map the metadata to the DCAT³⁴ model using mapping descriptions. The F2DS - Metadata repository is also linked to the ElasticSearch index created for this project in order to annotate the dataset with semantic concepts;

Finally, the mapped metadata is published into the Fair Data point repository.

4.3.4 Scenario 1: Public Galaxy instance(s)

The demonstrator service is a public Galaxy server. The implemented workflow is described above (up to the variant calling step). It has been selected to properly test the prototype, since it is not requiring a huge amount of resources (32GB RAM and 16 CPUs), but still data output can be used to validate our prototype. Moreover, since this workflow is commonly used to analyse human genetic data, currently under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), it can be used to properly test the third scenario as well.

Galaxy specification:

- Version: 20.05
- CPUs 16
- RAM: 32GB
- Storage: 500GB
- Tools: specific tools for variant detection installed (manually)
- Workflows: variant detection workflow

Deployment informations:

The EOSC-Pillar-T6.6 public server was deployed using the Laniakea development instance, which exploits the official Galaxy project Ansible roles to install and configure the service. The Pillar instance has been also configured to have a straight forward access to reference data mounting the official Galaxy CVMFS repository, using the Galaxy official Ansible role³⁵.

scenario realisation:

Selected dataset is published in Inserm Repository. It is then referenced in EOSC-Pillar F2DS (FAIR Datapoint), so as to be visible from the Catalogue (D4Science) side. The idea is then to get the API endpoint description to the physical dataset, present in the metadata read from the F2DS. On the consumer side, we can then chain Galaxy public server using this API, and import the dataset on the server to perform predefined workflow.

4.3.5 Scenario 2: Close-to-the-data deployment

This service uses a specific deployment of Laniakea and specific, on demand instances based on the Laniakea software that can be deployed on local machines.

Galaxy specification:

- Version: 20.05
- Tools: specific tools for variant detection installed
- Workflows: variant detection workflow

Deployment informations:

- Automatic deployment of «pillar-flavored» VM on the cloud infrastructure

³⁴<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

³⁵<https://galaxy.ansible.com/galaxyproject/cvmfs>

- RAM 32Gb 16vcpus Storage

Scenario realisation:

Galaxy-Laniakea is deployed locally. Dataset's metadata are obtained from EOSC-Pillar F2DS, yet in this scenario, data import is also done locally (the starting point of this scenario being that Galaxy runs close to the data - possibly with local import possible). Selected Galaxy workflow is then run similarly to scenario 1.

A full working demo of the Laniakea software used as part of the 6.6 usecase is available online³⁶

4.3.6 Scenario 3: Health data with restricted access

This scenario highlights the need to define specific requirements linked to the manipulation of sensitive data (patient data and personal information). Legal and ethical requirements are needed in order to comply with the legal framework and to remove obstacles to data sharing and interoperability, according to the FAIR and Open Science principles. The research activities take into account the differences between the French Legal Order and the Italian Legal Order on this topic, in the transnational context. In the context of T6.6, a complete report of this work ("Legal Framework for the use and re-use of health data for scientific purposes") has been produced and is available online³⁷.

This document aims to:

- define the Legal Framework for the use and re-use of health data for scientific purposes;
- outline the most important gap deriving from the differences between National laws concerning the processing of health data and the possible solution;
- suggest a guide for researchers involved in this scenario

Working in vision of the scenario 3, the Laniakea management of sensitive data has been improved by redesigning the system for volumes encryption implemented in Laniakea v2.0.0. The Laniakea encryption module has been completely reworked to port the system, previously developed in Python 2 and bash, to Python 3 and make the encryption process simpler and more linear to perform and maintain. All the components needed to encrypt the volume, mount it, and the API required for controlling the encryption process through the Laniakea dashboard were implemented and made available through the development of a Python package called PyLUKS³⁸, installable using pip. The new volume encryption strategy has been generalized and can now be applied also to applications other than Galaxy, and can be used with all the present and future applications supported by Laniakea. This update provides a more manageable solution for storage encryption and its management, which has been proven to be useful for data protection for both Laniakea and other research contexts.

Laniakea exploits the INDIGO Cloud Orchestration system (PaaS layer) for Galaxy deployments, which has been extended to be able to manage the creation of virtual environments on a private network, taking advantage of the isolation of virtual networks

³⁶https://youtu.be/SK9C_MWz6Yk

³⁷<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334878>

³⁸<https://pypi.org/project/pyluks/>

at the tenant level guaranteed by the cloud provider and automatically configuring appropriate security groups that monitor network traffic. In this way, access to the various analysis environments is blocked from the external network and also the traffic between virtual machines instantiated on the same private network, but belonging to different deployments, is filtered. The access to the service is provided to users through a VPN server at the tenant level. VPN users authentication is performed using INDIGO-IAM, i.e. using the same credentials exploited to access Laniakea, which greatly improves the user experience, since no additional account has to be created. In particular, the solution implemented for the VPN is based on the OpenVPN open source software and on a PAM module developed ad-hoc to allow authentication via IAM. The solutions described have been tested and validated on the ReCaS-Bari³⁹ cloud and on the INFN-Cloud⁴⁰ multi-site distributed infrastructure.

4.3.7 Scenario 4: Reproducibility and verification

This comparison scenario runs as follows:

- Publish in EOSC-Pillar F2DS dataset described in section 4.2.3
- Gather metadata from the F2DS to get access to the dataset through publisher's API
- Run Galaxy workflow described in section 4.3.2:
 - on Laniakea@ReCAS (scenario 1)
 - on a locally deployed instance (scenario 2)
 - on INFN secured infrastructure (scenario 3)
- Collect outputs of the 3 runs above
- Compare files and realise a gap analysis in case of differences
- Assess differences if any

Despite being theoretically designed, this scenario has actually not been fully implemented during the project because of a lack of dedicated resources in the final year. The last 2 steps (comparison and gap analysis) remain to be realised.

4.4 Building a demonstrator on the hCNV application

4.4.1 Proposed environment/architecture

In order to address the optimisation and reproducibility issue, the idea is to implement both the analysis and the comparison workflows within the Galaxy platform . To do so, we propose to make use of the tools and architecture designed and used within EOSC-Pillar usecase 6, namely the FAIR Federated Data Space (F2DS) provided within WP5, and the Laniakea Galaxy service provided as part of the T7.4 task.

³⁹<https://www.recas-bari.it/index.php/en/>

⁴⁰<https://www.cloud.infn.it/>

4.4.2 Proposed scenario

The whole scientific scenario is described in the following figure.

The scientific scenario follows these steps:

1. We select 2 samples within the set of NIST reference data
2. We get a copy of one of those samples in INSERM repository, and then reference it in the F2DS (FAIR datapoint/producer side)
3. The second sample is referenced in the F2DS directly pointing to its location on NIST database
4. We also reference in the F2DS the output files (VCF format) that corresponds to the NIST gold standard
5. We run the analysis workflows on Laniakea, using as input those samples gathered from the F2DS (catalogue/consumer side)
6. We run the comparison workflow to compare obtained results on Lanikea with Gold Standard results
7. We publish the result of the comparison (statistic table) in Inserm repository, and reference it in the F2DS

Note that using 2 samples and storing them in a different place (steps 2 and 3) is not mandatory for benchmarking purposes, but running the workflow using different endpoints as data sources will allow us to check that it can run in similar conditions independently of the data source location.

4.4.3 Used data

We propose to use the data available from The Genome in a Bottle project⁴¹ as a basis for the study, and will select 2 samples from the “Ashkenazim trio”, from the same individual (son,HG002) and produced via different sequencing techniques:

- Illumina WGS 2x150bp 300X per individual, novoalign HG002.
- Illumina WGS 2X250bp, novoalign HG002.

While it would be more representative to start from data in the fastq format, because of time constraints we will skip the alignment part and use data available in the bam format directly.

4.4.4 Used Tools

Aim is to run the benchmark on the following CNV callers:

- Control_FREEC⁴²
- Lumpy⁴³
- GATK4_mutect2⁴⁴

Results comparison workflow (comparing benchmark results with NISC gold standard) can be made using the Truvari⁴⁵ tool .

4.4.5 Feedback and perspectives

The concrete implementation of this workflow faced a technical problem in the huge size of source files. The resources used as part of the EOSC-Pillar project did not allow for enough RAM memory to actually perform the whole processing.

While this can be solved easily by increasing the resources behind used tools, this highlights the fact that scalability is a major point when going from a demonstrator to a real-life scientific application.

⁴¹https://github.com/genome-in-a-bottle/giab_data_indexes

⁴²<https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btr670>

⁴³<https://doi.org/10.1186/gb-2014-15-6-r84>

⁴⁴<https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/hc/en-us/articles/5358911630107-Mutect2>

⁴⁵<https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.02.21.481353>

5 Conclusion

5.1 Usecase outputs

5.1.1 Key exploitable results

The following Key exploitable Results (KER) are listed as part of WP6 final report for usecase 6:

- Improvement of the Laniakea software based on scientific and operational workflows defined within the usecase⁴⁶
- Full report on Legal Framework for the use and re-use of health data for scientific purposes⁴⁷
- Application of the metadata enrichment process elaborated within WP5, with concrete plans to implement and reuse such system at institutional level

These results are described in more details in the following sections.

5.1.2 Services and tools

The main visible output of the usecase is the set of improvements made to the Laniakea software, following tests and implementation of our various scenarios.

The Laniakea is a free and open method for delivering Galaxy "on-demand" instances across various cloud infrastructures. The ELIXIR-ITALY Laniakea@ReCaS offers access to Cloud resources to be used for the deployment of on-demand Galaxy instances, ready for production, with reference data and tools already pre-configured and ready to be used. A user-friendly interface is provided for users to configure, launch, and manage their Galaxy instance(s) on the Cloud. For that, it was crucial to suggest the various guidelines and best practices for using and deploying Galaxy.

5.1.3 Guidelines and best practices

The Galaxy portal can be used for a variety of purposes, ranging from a single-user portal to a production portal. During the different phases of the project and based on the diverse needs of researchers, various methods of deploying the Galaxy were proposed and explained. This work has been fed back to the Elixir Galaxy community.

Along with the descriptions and instructions for using the various services, a user manual for the data was also provided. Based on suggested guidelines and links to use and reuse, data protection, and the best repository based on the type of data, researchers were directed.

The most concrete output in this regards is the document published on Legal Framework for the use and re-use of health data for scientific purposes, cited and referenced in section 5.1.1. Making health data FAIR remains a major challenge, and this document is a concrete step towards facilitating this at a transnational level.

⁴⁶<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1118635.1>

⁴⁷<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334878>

5.1.4 Outreach and community involvement

While building our usecase, we had extensive contacts with French representatives of the Elixir hCNV community, as described above. This is not something that was foreseen at the beginning of the project, and can be considered an outreach activity. This allowed one of T6.6 members to contribute in September 2020 to Elixir Europe Biohackaton⁴⁸.

In parallel, work done around Galaxy as part of T6.6 has led to consider a collaboration with the EOSC-Life project⁴⁹, which resulted in a signed collaboration agreement between EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Life in August 2022. Both projects are collaborating to provide on-demand Galaxy instances, and beyond, in isolated cloud environments, accessible only through virtual VPN by users. This, together with the on-demand Storage Encryption already in place, would provide the possibility to deploy secure instances suitable for sensitive data analysis. Being Laniakea among the EOSC-Life WP7 managed services, these improvements will be available to both communities.

Finally, one of the most visible outputs of the usecase is the set of online resources and contributions to various events. All documents, publications, posters and presentations are listed and presented in appendix A.

5.1.5 Remaining blocking points

The project was created to give researchers the chance to publish their datasets fairly and to enrich their metadata. It is a project based on various services collected from various partners; connecting these services is a bit of a challenge. We got stuck while trying to implement the various scenarios because connecting Galaxy to the D4science catalog is not straightforward. This difficulty is explained by the fact that the two proposed services use different AAI protocols.

We encountered a second restriction when testing the various scenarios using the hCNV dataset: the test version of the GALAXY service has a 32GB memory size limit. The dataset is so large that testing the workflow with it necessitates an increase in Galaxy memory space. We became aware of these blocking points after conducting numerous tests, and we worked to find solutions.

5.2 Possible future work

5.2.1 Follow up on project actions

Services developed within EOSC-PILLAR still have a lot of room for improvement. In that regard, it might prove interesting to carry on planned developments and realisations that have not been entirely completed during the project's lifetime.

Within Usecase 6, scenario 4 has not been fully implemented, and it would make sense to do so, using the service prototypes that have been developed. The primary objectives of scenario 4 are reproducibility and verification. It aims to test how different services respond to the same workflow under various conditions.

As a follow-up work, we could also mention the possibility to extend guidelines for the deployment and use of the Galaxy service to IFB instance. Getting IFB galaxy service

⁴⁸<https://github.com/elixir-europe/BioHackathon-projects-2020/tree/master/projects/7>

⁴⁹<https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

through the EOSC onboarding procedure could be of benefit.

Finally, it would be worth paying close attention to the various ideas and suggestions presented within the framework of EOSC-Pillar/EOSC-Life collaboration agreement. The work done as part of T6.6 on Galaxy prompted consideration of a collaboration with the EOSC-Life project have to be continued.

5.2.2 Exploitation of key results

One of the most beneficial outcomes of implementing usecase 6 is the ability to enrich metadata. Because it is not always possible to include or add metadata when publishing a dataset in a repository, finding a way to enrich the metadata of these datasets is critical. One of EOSC-Pillar's main output, the F2DS made-to-order service, aids in retrieving data and enhancing its metadata so that it can subsequently be published in a metadata repository.

This could be further exploited in another context, possibly at institutional level, where the service could be offered to a various range of users to improve the quality of the metadata they publish.

Another key output that is worth capitalizing on, is the set of best practices and documentations that have been produced. Training and support actions in the field of Research Data Management would benefit from this documentation.

Finally, on the technical side, the re-use of various services developed or improved within the project should be encouraged. While the target is reached with regards to the Laniakea@ReCaS service, gained expertise on building and providing a Galaxy service (for example in the context of a secured infrastructure) could be more exploited in France. The same is true with regards to technical services and best practices that led to the establishment of Inserm's institutional repository, that can benefit from all the work done here.

5.2.3 potential use by other communities

While UC6 was designed based on the needs of the bioinformatics community, the theoretical scenarios, practical scientific scenario, service prototypes and implementation reports produced as part of this use case can be extended to other communities. Galaxy is widely used in other disciplines ranging from agricultural and food to environmental sciences, and UC6 work can be of interest for those communities. Going beyond the tools themselves, lessons learned from building a data usage scenario on top of EOSC-Pillar services can translate to a wide range of solutions where the challenges are the same, i.e. link source and reference data to computational and analysis tools in a coherent way.

A Deliverables, online resources and documentation

A.1 Online resources and project deliverables

The following table lists the different documents that have been produced as an output of the T6.6 task, either as stand-alone documents, or as part of project deliverables.

Title	Comments	Link
UC6.6 factsheet	Use case web description	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6726022
UC6.6 Demo	Demo provided as communication medium for the project website	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WZey8XrCp1I
Laniakea Demo	available online and used as part of the 6.6 usecase	https://youtu.be/SK9C_MWz6Yk
UC6.6 poster (Dec.2021)	presented at JCAD 2021 conference	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5764786
UC6.6 poster (Sep.2022)	presented at EGI 2022 conference	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051283
Legal Framework for the use and re-use of health data for scientific purposes	Complete report from scenario 3 by Nadina Foggetti, Giacinto Donvito, & Marco Antonio Tangaro (2022)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334878
EOSC-Pillar collection on Zenodo	Publicly available project results	https://zenodo.org/communities/eosc-pillar/

A.2 Presentations, talks and posters during events

Event	Description & Link
French EOSC Days at CNRS (Jan. 2020)	Short presentation and contribution to the global discussion. https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/eosc-pillar-eosc-day-cnrs-paris
EOSC-hub week (May 2020)	Short talk. https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/eosc-hub-week-2020
Galaxy Community Conference 2021 (Jul. 2021)	talk: Marco Antonio Tangaro, Giacinto Donvito, Marica Antonacci, Matteo Chiara, Pietro Mandreoli et al. “Laniakea – Update 2021”. F1000Research 2021, 10:636 (slides). https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1118635.1
PhD workshop UNIMI (Oct. 2021)	Poster: Pietro Mandreoli, Marco Antonio Tangaro et al “Laniakea: Shaping and Developing a Cloud-based bioinformatic platform” PhD Workshop 2021 UNIMI, 7-8 October 2021. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6206807
JCAD2021 (Dec. 2021)	Poster: Sanaa, Yosra, Mathieu, Gilles, et al. (2021). Exploring reference data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics community. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5764786
WALS2022 (Jul. 2022)	Talk: Marco Antonio Tangaro, Marica Antonacci, Pietro Mandreoli, Daniele Colombo, Nadina Foggetti, Giacinto Donvito, Graziano Pesole, Federico Zambelli “The Laniakea Dashboard and storage encryption components: a foundation for developing on-demand cloud services for Life Science”. https://icwe2022.webengineering.org/wals2022/
EGI2022 (Sep. 2022)	Poster: Sanaa, Yosra, Belhaj Salem, Marwa, Mathieu, Gilles, et al. (2022). Exploring reference data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics community. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051283
JCAD2022 (Oct. 2022)	Talk: Gilles Mathieu, Marwa Belhaj Salem. Retour d’expérience sur le développement d’un cas d’usage en bioinformatique au sein du projet EOSC-Pillar. https://jcad2022.sciencesconf.org/
EOSC-Pillar final conference (Oct. 2022)	Talk: Gilles Mathieu, Marwa Belhaj Salem : Technical Track - Biomedical Usecase https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/sites/default/files/S3_4_Concrete_cases_Gilles.pdf

B Annexes

B.1 Data formats

B.1.1 Sequence data

Fasta

- Used to store sequences of DNA, RNA or protein
- First line starts with the > and contains a description of the sequence
- Several sequences can be stored in a given .fasta
- Following lines contain the sequence (with a fixed maximum number of characters per line (60, 70 or 80 characters))

```
1 >BT006808.1 Homo sapiens insulin mRNA, complete cds
2 ATGGCCCTGTGGATGCGCCTCCTGCCCTGCTGGCGCTGCTGGCCCTCTGGGGACCTGACCCAGCCGCAG
3 CCTTTGTGAACCAACACCTGTGCGGCTCACACCTGGTGGAAGCTCTCTACCTAGTGTGCGGGAACGAGG
4 CTTCTTCTACACACCCAAGACCCGCCGGGAGGCAGAGGACCTGCAGGTGGGGCAGGTGGAGCTGGGCGGG
5 GGCCCTGGTGCAGGCAGCCTGCAGCCCTTGGCCCTGGAGGGTCCCTGCAGAAGCGTGGCATTGTGGAAC
6 AATGCTGTACCAGCATCTGCTCCCTCTACCAGCTGGAGAACTACTGCAACTAG
```

FastQ

- A fusion between a .fasta file and a file that contains the quality indicators of the sequence provided by the sequencer
- Encoded with a single ASCII character
- 4 lines per sequences :
 - @ : identifier of the sequence
 - sequence of the read
 - + : commentary, optional
 - quality values for the sequence on line 1

```
@SEQ_ID
GATTTGGGGTTCAAAGCAGTATCGATCAAATAGTAAATCCATTTGTTCAACTCACAGTTT
+
!' '*((( (**+))%%++) (%%%) .1***-+* '))**55CCF>>>>>CCCCCCC65
```

B.1.2 Genome Annotations

.gtf

- Genome is usually annotated in terms of genes and transcripts
- Provides informations about the exon-intron structure
- Special format file : .gtf

<u>Ch name</u>	<u>feature type</u>		<u>end position</u>		<u>strand of the feature</u>			<u>attribute</u>
<u>Col 1</u>	<u>Col 2</u>	<u>Col 3</u>	<u>Col 4</u>	<u>Col 5</u>	<u>Col 6</u>	<u>Col 7</u>	<u>Col 8</u>	<u>Col 9</u>
chr21	HAVANA	transcript	10862622	10863067	.	+	.	gene_id "ENSG00000169..
chr21	HAVANA	exon	10862622	10862667	.	+	.	gene_id "ENSG00000169..
chr21	HAVANA	CDS	10862622	10862667	.	+	0	gene_id "ENSG00000169..
chr21	HAVANA	start_codon	10862622	10862624	.	+	0	gene_id "ENSG00000169..
chr21	HAVANA	exon	10862751	10863067	.	+	.	gene_id "ENSG00000169..
chr21	HAVANA	CDS	10862751	10863064	.	+	2	gene_id "ENSG00000169..
chr21	HAVANA	stop_codon	10863065	10863067	.	+	0	gene_id "ENSG00000169..
chr21	HAVANA	UTR	10863065	10863067	.	+	.	gene_id "ENSG00000169..

Source of the data (points to Col 1)
start position (points to Col 3)
score (points to Col 6)
indicates which base of the feature is the first of a codon (points to Col 7)

B.1.3 Data for mapping

SAM

- It is generated as a human readable version of BAM format
- A tab-delimited text format consisting of a header section
- Header lines start with @
- Each alignment line has 11 mandatory fields

Bam file

- The compressed binary version of a SAM file
- The header contains informations about the entire file (sample name and length, alignment method)
- The alignments contain read
- Contain informations about the position of each read in the reference genome

B.1.4 General Formats

BED

- Define the data lines that are displayed in an annotation track
- Have three required fields and nine additional optional fields

BigWig

- Files are in an indexed binary format
- For display of dense, continuous data that will be displayed in the Genome Browser as a graph

VCF (Varian Call Format)

- A flexible and extendable format for variation data
- Can be displayed on the Genome Browser

B.2 Existing data sources in bioinformatics

A database is a set of organized, searchable, routinely updated, and cross-referenced data. It houses electronic biological data storage for genomic, proteomic, and microarray gene expression data. There are various types of databases depending on the type of data: databases for the genome, sequences, structures, and chemicals.. Access to these databases may be open to the public, subject to copy right restrictions, limited to browsing, or available only for viewing.

types of databases

Primary databases	Secondary databases
Contains original data from researchers	Contains data derived from the results of analysing primary data
Experimental results are submitted directly into the database by researchers, and the data are essentially archival in nature	Manually created or automatically generated
Once given a database accession number, the data in primary database are never changed	Contains more relevant and useful information structured to specific requirements
Public or open access mostly	Access depending on the database
Examples : for DNA/RNA sequences : GeneBank, EMBL and DDBG ; for protein sequences: SWISS-PROT, PIR, COGs, Uni-Prot ; for molecular structures: PDB	Examples: PROSITE, PRINTS, BLOCKS, Pfam. . .

Primary database : (open access)

Databases	Features	Data
GenBank	The genetic sequence database at the National Center For Biotechnology Information (NCBI) is part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (which comprises DDBJ, ENA, GenBank). It contains nucleotide sequences for more than 240 000 organisms	DNA/RNA sequences
EMBL	European Molecular Biological Laboratory Nucleic acid database from EBI (European Bioinformatics Institute) Product in collaboration with DDBJ and GenBank Search engine – SRS (Sequence Retrieval System)	DNA/RNA sequences
DDBJ	DNA Databank of Japan Nucleotide sequence database In collaboration with GenBank Produced and maintained at NIG (National Institute of Genetics)	DNA/RNA sequences
SWISS PROT	Annotated sequence database Consists of sequence entries of different life formats Similar format to EMBL Output format is swiss-prot file	protein sequences
PIR	Protein Information Resource A division of National Biomedical Research Foundation (NBRF)	protein sequences

Secondary databases

Databases	Features	Data	Primary source
PROSITE	Families of proteins Can search using regular expressions	Regular expression	SWISS PROT
BLOCKS	Motifs/blocks are created by automatically detecting the most conserved regions of each protein family.	Aligned motifs (blocks)	PROSITE/PRINTS
PRINTS	Most protein families are characterized not by one, but by several conserved motifs. Fingerprints are groups of conserved motifs excised from sequence alignments.	Aligned motifs	OWL(Composite DB)
Pfam	Maintained by the Sanger Centre Protein families aligned using HMMS Give a new sequence	Hidden Markov Models(HMM)	SWISS PROT